

101034439 - Resolution

Medical Genetic Solutions for RESOLUTE

WP1 – Collection and annotation of SLC human genetics data

D1.6 Genetic assessment of all SLC family members

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.1	09 May 2022	Final version
V2.0	16 Sep 2022	Revised version upon PO feedback (update of section “repository for primary data”)

Abstract

The genetic evaluation of genes and variants is based on a comprehensive interpretation of the collected data in two steps. The first step includes a rough pre-sorting of the family members. Findings from all sources are summarized in a genetic score which offers a ranking of all SLCs and focus on missense and loss of function variants. Open Targets overall association score is a general ranking approach (e.g., including non-coding variants) which classifies the SLC in therapeutic field including genetic associations, somatic mutations, drugs, pathways and systems biology, text mining, RNA expression and animal models. This score contains the genetic associations per SLC in the therapeutic area. These two scores can narrow down the potential SLCs for further detailed curation. After a pre-selection has been made, a manual evaluation can then be carried out as a second step. For this purpose, it is evaluated whether missense or loss of function variants are related to rare or civilization diseases, relevant intermediate biomarkers and whether these indications result in a coherent profile e.g., with the expression tissue.

Methods

Step 1 - pre-sorting of the family members

The genetic assessment starts with a pre-selection of SLCs based on two different scores for manual curation. Results from data mining workflow are summarized in a genetic score which offers a ranking of all SLCs. A large value indicates there is strong genetic evidence found in the data sources. This score has a focus on missense/loss of function variants, which can alter protein function and structure.

Distribution of genetic evidence score across all 456 SLCs:

Open targets overall association score classifies the SLCs in disease/phenotype categories. This score considers genetic associations e.g., non-coding variants, somatic mutations, drugs, pathways and systems biology, text mining, RNA expression and animal models. Each SLC is rated (0-1) within the therapeutic area. A prefilter is set to 0.3 and all SLCs which are already known as drug targets are excluded. These two scores can narrow down the potential SLCs for further detailed curation. It is thus possible to select a diverse panel of SLCs and each partner has the chance to set an individual focus during the selection process.

Overview of therapeutic field (count of SLC):

Biological process (22)
Cancer (22)
Benign neoplasm (2)
Cardiovascular (29)
Visual system (37)
Endocrine system (45)
Gastrointestinal (53)
Genetic familial or congenital (53)
Hematologic (17)
Immune system (31)
Infectious (15)
Infectious disease or post-infectious disorder (15)
Integumentary system (33)
Measurement (213)
Musculoskeletal or connective tissue (66)
Nervous system (98)
Nutritional or metabolic (95)
Pancreas (26)
Phenotype (59)
Psychiatric disorder (39)
Reproductive system (13)
Respiratory or thoracic (44)
Urinary system (33)
Breast (3)

Step 2 – manual curation of the pre-selected family members

In the next step, the pre-selected candidates are assessed in more detail. Missense or loss of function variants are evaluated for associations and /or reported relationships in rare and civilization diseases or relevant intermediate biomarkers. For this purpose, the collected variants for large scale genome wide experiments (DNA, RNA, protein, and metabolite associations), gene-based and single-variant tests for rare variants, curated data and biomedical literature are used. A collection of missense and loss of function variants with

disease/phenotype associations in combination with the expression profile, ideally in a specific tissue can support the final selection step. If the evidence paints a coherent picture, the SLCs is shortlisted.

Results

The selection spreadsheets contain gathered data for all 456 SLCs in a compressed format. Hits in different sources are coded in a binary format and summarized in genetic evidence score and open targets overall genetic association score. The detailed evaluation is done with collected data for different sources.

Conclusion

A twostep approach is used to shortlist favorite SLCs with an individual focus during the selection process:

1. Pre-selection with two different scores

- Genetic score focused on missense variants in different sources
- Overall genetic association score covering general genetic associations, somatic mutations, drugs, pathways and systems biology, text mining, RNA expression and animal models from open targets

2. Detailed curation at the variant-level traits.

- Evaluation of missense and loss of function variants for associations and /or reported relationships in rare and civilization diseases or relevant intermediate biomarkers
- Expression tissue

Repository for primary data

The RESOLUTE/REsolution web portal will act as the repository for the SLC genetic data. The genetic variant information and the collection of human disease association will be included in the RESOLUTE/REsolution knowledgebase and made publicly available for each SLC in the respective web pages (<https://re-solute.eu/knowledgebase/gene>). The genetic score will be made available in the shape of a dynamic dashboard (<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards/genetic-score>).